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Abstract book

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Late toxicity and cosmetic outcome of ultra-hypofractionated radiotherapy of breast cancer

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Background and Objectives: Minimizing radiation induced tissue toxicity is one of the most important issues in breast cancer patients. The study aimed to investigate late normal tissue toxicity and cosmetic results between moderated and ultra-fractionated regimes for early breast cancer patients.

Materials and Methods: This prospective randomized study included 60 patients with early breast cancer after preserving surgery, 27 patients advocated to ultra-hypofractionated whole-breast three dimensional (3D) conformal radiotherapy of 26 Gy in 5 fractions over 1 week and 33 patients with moderate fractionated breast 3D conformal radiotherapy of 40 Gy in 15 fractions over 3 weeks between March 2020 and July 2020. Dosimetric parameters for lung and heart doses were compared between two groups. Late skin toxicity, subcutaneous tissue toxicity, pulmonary toxicity, heart toxicity and cosmetic results of two regimes were analyzed and compared.

Results: Median follow-up was 40 months. Dosimetric results revealed that patients in 5 fraction group received significantly lower median ipsilateral lung doses ($p < 0.01$) in addition to left breast cancer patients that received significantly lower median heart dose ($p < 0.01$) and median LAD dose ($p < 0.01$). When two regimes were compared, there was no statistically significant difference in late skin toxicity ($p = 0.399$). Subcutaneous tissue toxicity was similar in two groups ($p = 0.270$). Late pulmonary toxicity didn't significantly differ in the 5 fraction regime compared to 15 fractions regime ($p = 0.362$). There was no statistically difference in late heart toxicity when two groups were compared ($p = 0.362$). Cosmetic results were similar in the both groups ($p = 0.46$).

Conclusion: Ultra-hypofractionated radiotherapy for breast cancer is non-inferior compared to the moderate hypofractionation regime regarding late skin toxicity, subcutaneous tissue toxicity, late pulmonary and

heart toxicity and cosmetic results. Application of ultra-hypofractionated radiotherapy significantly lowers radiation doses to lung and heart and could be significant in prevention of late radiotherapy complications.

Keywords: radiotherapy, ultra-hypofractionated radiotherapy, breast cancer

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